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Turning climate-related information into added value for traditional **MED**iterranean **GRAPE**, **OL**ive and **DURUM** wheat food systems

***Report on the Final release of the tool for the wine sector
(Deliverable 3.8)***

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All partners involved in the production/implementation of the deliverable should comment and report (if needed) in the above table. The above table should support the decisions made for the specific deliverable in order to include the agreement of all involved parties for the final version of the document.

Finally, after the peer review process, the deliverable should be modified accordingly to the comments and the reflections to the comments should be reported in the above table.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a report on the set of codes, tools and usage examples included in the [wine service repository](#) (base for the generation of the information within the MED-GOLD wine service [platform](#) and [Dashboard](#)). It describes the contents of the four folders in which the repository has been structured: Historical Climate, Seasonal Forecasts, Climate Projections and Climate Indices. The objective of this repository is to ensure the replicability of most of the data included in the Wine Service [platform](#) and [Dashboard](#), not only for the wine sector but also for other sectors.

1. OBJECTIVES

With this deliverable, the project has contributed to the achievement of the following objectives (DOA, PartB Table1.1):

No.	Objective	Yes
1	To co-design, co-develop, test, and assess the added value of proof-of-concept climate services for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
2	To refine, validate, and upscale the three pilot services with the wider European and global user communities for olive, grape, and durum wheat	
3	To ensure replicability of MED-GOLD climate services in other crops/climates (e.g., coffee) and to establish links to policy making globally	X
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	

2. IMPACT

No.	Expected impact	Yes
1	Providing added-value for the decision-making process addressed by the project, in terms of effectiveness, value creation, optimised opportunities and minimising risk	
2	Enhancing the potential for market uptake of climate services demonstrated by addressing the added value	
3	Ensuring the replicability of the methodological frameworks for value added climate services in potential end-user markets	Provision of an open repository with the codes to compute bioclimatic indicators and compound risk indices for different time-scales: historical, seasonal predictions and climate projections.
4	To implement a comprehensive communication and commercialization plan for MED-GOLD climate services to enhance market uptake	
5	To build better informed and connected end-user communities for the global olive oil, wine, and pasta food systems and related policy making	

3. DEFINITIONS

Concepts and terms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table (some of these definitions along with others relevant for the project can be also found in the [MED-GOLD glossary](#)):

Table 1-1 Definitions.

Concept / Term	Definition
Bias	The model error(s) in simulated climate, when compared with observations.
Climate change projections	Climate scenarios for the future, commonly, for the next century
Bioclimatic indices	Parameters describing a specific characteristic of climate (e.g. intensity, frequency or distribution) for the agricultural sector
Dashboard	Integrated visualization display
Essential Climate Variables	A group of variables that critically contributes to the characterization of Earth's climate. For the surface, the variables include air temperature, precipitation, humidity, wind speed and direction, etc.
Indicator	A parameter describing a reality, i.e., synthesizing the effects of future climate change with relevance to a specific sector and business
Matlab	MATLAB is a proprietary multi-paradigm programming language and numeric computing environment developed by MathWorks.
Python	Python is an interpreted high-level general-purpose programming language. It is supported by the Python Software Foundation.
R	R is a programming language and free software environment for statistical computing and graphics supported by the R Foundation for Statistical Computing
Repository	A central location in which a certain amount of data and/or code is stored and managed.
Seasonal forecasts	Predictions of the climatic conditions for the coming months

4. ACRONYMS

Acronyms used in this document and needing a definition are included in the following table:

Table 1-2 Acronyms and abbreviations.

Acronym	Definition
CDS-C3S	Climate Data Store - Copernicus Climate Change Service
ERA5	ECMWF Atmospheric ReAnalysis 5
GDD	Growing Degree Days
GST	Growing Season average Temperature
HarvestR	Harvest total precipitation
SprR	Spring total precipitation
SEAS5	ECMWF Seasonal Forecasting System 5
SU35	Number of heat stress days
WSDI	Warm Spell Duration Index

5. REFERENCES

The following documents, although not part of this document, amplify or clarify its contents. Reference documents are those not applicable and referenced within this document. They are referenced in this document in the form [RD.x]:

Ref.	Title	Code	Version	Date
[RD.1]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 3.2: Report on the methodology followed to implement the wine pilot services			2020
[RD.2]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 3.6: First feedback report from users on wine pilot service development			2019
[RD.3]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 3.7: Second Feedback report from users on wine pilot service development			2020
[RD.4]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 3.3: Report on the climatic, bioclimatic and extreme climate indices developed in the wine pilot services			2021
[RD.5]	MED-GOLD Deliverable 3.5: A handy easy-to-use manual for stakeholders and practitioners of the climate service tool. PART II: the grape/ wine sector			2021

6. WINE SERVICE REPOSITORY

6.1 Introduction

The wine service repository contains the main functions and scripts that have been used to generate the contents offered in the MED-GOLD wine dashboard. It is organised in four folders that include codes and, in some cases, examples of use. The aforementioned folders are as follows.

- Historical climate
- Seasonal forecasts
- Climate projections
- Climate indices

6.2 Historical Climate

The [‘Historical Climate’](#) includes the scripts providing the main outcomes in the “Historical climate” tab of the Dashboard (bioclimatic indicators and compound risk indexes). In particular, the scripts include the general procedure to, firstly, download hourly climate Data from CDS (with particular attention devoted to the ERA5 Reanalysis System), to compute the bio-climatic indicators and compound risk indexes, and finally to process data to be directly ingested in the MED-GOLD Dashboard system. More details for each script are reported in the Readme.txt file in the folder “Historical Climate”.

The bioclimatic indicators selected, along with the compound wine risk indexes have been exhaustively described in ([RD.1], [RD.2] and [RD.3]), while their main climatological features, as described in ERA5 datasets for the region of interest of MED-GOLD Wine service have been reported in [RD.4]. The main functionalities of the Dashboard, including the main options for the “Historical Climate” tab have been reported in the User Guide [RD.5]

The Scripts are written in Matlab programming language, Shell scripts and Python. They also require CDO, a collection of command line Operators to manipulate and analyse Climate and NWP model Data (see <https://code.mpimet.mpg.de/projects/cdo/>)

6.3 Seasonal Forecasts

The '[Seasonal Forecasts](#)' comprises the atomic functions that allows the calculation of the bioclimatic indicators in the "Seasonal Forecast" tab of the Dashboard. These atomic functions are within the open source CSIndicators R package which has been developed by the BSC in the framework of the current H2020 MED-GOLD project (776467). This package is publicly available at CRAN and contains a set of generalised methods for the flexible computation of user-defined climate related indicators specifically developed for seasonal climate predictions.

Each method represents a specific mathematical approach to define the indicator which allows the possibility of selecting an arbitrary time period for the calculation of the indicator. This enables a wide range of possibilities to tailor the most suitable indicator for the specific needs of the wine sector and also the adaptation to any other particular agriculture sector or climate service application (food security, energy, water management, etc). Although this package is intended for seasonal climate predictions, its methods are also applicable to other time-scales such as sub-seasonal or decadal. Additionally, the outputs of the functions in this package are compatible with the R package 'CSTools', which is a widely used package for the forecast quality assessment and postprocessing of seasonal climate predictions.

In total there are 25 functions available within the package which are specifically described in the accompanying [pdf manual](#). The package also contains a vignette where the 10 MED-GOLD bioclimatic indicators (6 corresponding to the wine case) are documented and detailed steps for the computation are explained in an easy way to guide potential future users beyond the MED-GOLD project.

In the following lines we will show, as an example, the vignettes of two indicators, namely Spring Rain (SprR) and Growing Season Temperature (GST). The rest of the vignettes are accessible in the package Readme file. The definition of the bioclimatic indicators selected as well as their seasonal forecast quality assessment are described in [RD.1], [RD.2] and [RD.3], while their main climatological features have been reported in [RD.4]. Regarding the main functionalities of the Dashboard, including the main options for the "Seasonal Forecast" tab have been reported in the User Guide [RD.5].

6.3.1 VIGNETTE FOR THE COMPUTATION OF THE WINE SERVICE BIOCLIMATIC INDICATORS IN THE SEASONAL FORECAST FRAMEWORK

In the MED-GOLD seasonal forecast wine service a total of 6 bioclimatic indicators have been identified, whose calculation has been done based on several functions from the CSIndicators R package. The functions used and the corresponding indicators are listed as follows:

1. **PeriodAccumulation** - Spring Total Precipitation (SprR) and Harvest Total Precipitation (HarvestR)
2. **PeriodMean** - Growing Season Temperature (GST)
3. **TotalTimeExceedingThreshold** - Number of Heat Stress Days - 35°C (SU35)

-
4. **AccumulationExceedingThreshold** - Growing Degree Days (GDD)
 5. **TotalSpellTimeExceedingThreshold** - Warm Spell Duration Index (WSDI)

The above functions can take both multidimensional arrays and the `s2dv_cube` objects (see note below). Taking `PeriodAccumulation` as an example, `**CST**PeriodAccumulation` handles `s2dv_cube` objects and `PeriodAccumulation` without the prefix can compute multidimensional arrays.

Note: `s2dv_cube` and `array` classes can be handled by the functions in `CSIndicators`. See Section 2 in vignette [Data retrieval and storage](#) from `CSTools` R package for more information.

There are some supplementary functions which must be called to smoothly run the above functions.

1. **SelectPeriodOnData** - to select the data in the requested period
2. **SelectPeriodOnDates** - to select the time dimension in the requested period
3. **Threshold** - to convert absolute value/variable to its percentile, e.g., Warm Spell Duration Index uses the 90th percentile corresponding to each day instead of a fixed threshold.

When the period selection is required, the start and end parameters have to be provided to cut out the portion in `time_dim`. Otherwise, the function will take the entire `time_dim`. The examples of computing the aforementioned indicators are given by functions as follows. In this case we will present the vignette for the computation of a couple of these indicators: `SprR` and `GST`.

Spring Rain (SprR)

The `SprR` rain indicator (total precipitation from 21st April to 21st June) is important because dry springs will delay vegetative growth and reduce vigour and leaf area total surface. Fungal disease pressure will be lower and therefore there will be less need for protective and / or curative treatments, translating as less costs. Wet springs will promote higher vigour, increase the risk of fungal disease and disrupt vineyard operations as it may prevent machinery from getting in the vineyard due to mud. They are usually associated with higher costs.

First, load the required libraries, `CSIndicators`, `CSTools`, etc. by running

:

```
library(CSIndicators)
library(CSTools)
library(zeallot)
library(s2dv)
```

To obtain the precipitation forecast and observation, we load the daily precipitation (`prlr` given in `var`) data sets of ECMWF SEAS5 seasonal forecast and ERA5 reanalysis for the four starting dates 20130401-20160401 (provided in `sdates`) with the entire 7-month forecast time, April-October (214 days in total given in parameter `leadtimemax`).

The pathways of SEAS5 and ERA5 are given in the lists with some **whitecards (inside two dollar signs)** used to replace the variable name and iterative items such as year and month. See details of requirements in Section 4 in vignette [Data retrieval and storage](#) from CStools package.

The spatial domain covers part of Douro Valley of Northern Portugal lon=[352.25, 353], lat=[41, 41.75]. These four values are provided in lonmin, lonmax, latmin and latmax.

With the grid set to **r1440x721**, the SEAS5 forecast would be interpolated to the 0.25-degree ERA5 grid by using the **bicubic** method given in the method.

```
sdates <- paste0(2013:2016, '04', '01')

c(prlr_exp, prlr_obs) %<-% CST_Load(var = 'prlr',
                                   exp = list(S5path_prlr),
                                   obs = list(path_ERA5prlr_CDS),
                                   sdates = sdates,
                                   lonmax = 353, lonmin = 352.25,
                                   latmax = 41.75, latmin = 41,
                                   storefreq = 'daily',
                                   leaddtimemin = 1, leaddtimemax = 214,
                                   nmember = 3, output = "lonlat",
                                   grid = "r1440x721", method = 'bicubic')
```

The output contains data and metadata for the experiment and the observations. The elements `prlr_exp$data` and `prlr_obs$data` have dimensions:

```
dim(prlr_exp$data)
#dataset member  sdate  ftime   lat   lon
#      1      3      4    214     4     4
dim(prlr_obs$data)
#dataset member  sdate  ftime   lat   lon
#      1      1      4    214     4     4
```

To compute **SprR** of forecast and observation, we can run:

```
SprR_exp <- CST_PeriodAccumulation(prlr_exp, start = list(21, 4), end =
list(21, 6))
SprR_obs <- CST_PeriodAccumulation(prlr_obs, start = list(21, 4), end =
list(21, 6))
```


The start and end are the initial and final dates and the day must be given before the month as above. They will be applied along the dimension time_dim (it is set to 'ftime' by default). As mentioned, these parameters are optional, the function will take the entire time series when the period is not specified in start and end. The dimensions of SprR forecasts and observations are:

```
dim(SprR_exp$data)
#dataset member sdate lat lon
# 1 3 4 4 4
dim(SprR_obs$data)
#dataset member sdate lat lon
# 1 1 4 4 4
```

The forecast SprR for the 1st member from 2013-2016 of the 1st grid point in mm are:

```
SprR_exp$data[1,1,,1,1] * 86400 * 1000
#[1] 93.23205 230.41904 194.01412 226.52614
```

Growing Season Temperature (GST)

The growing Season Temperature, GST, is defined as the average of daily average temperatures between April 1st to October 31st in the Northern Hemisphere. It provides information on which are the best suited varieties for a given site or, inversely, which are the best places to grow a specific variety. For existing vineyards, GST also informs on the suitability of its varieties for the climate of specific years, explaining quality and production variation. Many grapevine varieties across the world have been characterized in function of their GST optimum.

Firstly, we prepare a sample data of daily mean temperature of SEAS5 and ERA5 data sets with the same starting dates, spatial domain, interpolation grid and method by running,

```
c(tas_exp, tas_obs) %<-% CST_Load(var = 'tas', exp = list(S5path), obs =
list(ERA5path),
sdates = sdates, lonmax = 353,
lonmin = 352.25,
latmax = 41.75, latmin = 41,
storefreq = 'daily',
leadtimemin = 1, leadtimemax = 214,
nmember = 3, output = "lonlat",
grid = "r1440x721", method = 'bicubic')
```


The output contains observations `tas_dvobsdata` and forecast `tas_dvexpdata`, and their dimensions and summaries are like,

```
dim(tas_obs$data)
#dataset member  sdate  ftime    lat    lon
#      1      1      4    214     4     4

dim(tas_exp$data)
#dataset member  sdate  ftime    lat    lon
#      1      3      4    214     4     4
```

```
summary(tas_obs$data - 273.15)
# Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
# 3.63  14.38  17.89  17.65  21.24  30.21

summary(tas_exp$data - 273.15)
# Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
# 0.54  11.65  16.56  16.50  21.25  31.41
```

To compute the GST for both observation and forecast, run the following lines,

```
# change the unit of temperature from °C to K
tas_exp$data <- tas_exp$data - 273.15
tas_obs$data <- tas_obs$data - 273.15
```

```
# compute GST
GST_exp <- CST_PeriodMean(tas_exp, start = list(1, 4), end = list(31, 10))
GST_obs <- CST_PeriodMean(tas_obs, start = list(1, 4), end = list(31, 10))
```

Since the period considered for GST is the entire period for the starting month of April, in this case the start and end parameters could be ignored. The summaries and dimensions of the output are as follows:

```
summary(GST_exp$data)
# Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
# 14.23  15.78  16.50  16.50  17.17  18.70

summary(GST_obs$data)
```



```
#   Min. 1st Qu.  Median    Mean 3rd Qu.    Max.
# 15.34  16.85   17.72   17.65  18.41   19.60
```

```
dim(GST_exp$data)
```

```
#dataset member  sdate    lat    lon
#         1      3      4      4      4
```

```
dim(GST_obs$data)
```

```
#dataset member  sdate    lat    lon
#         1      1      4      4      4
```

6.4 Climate Projections

In the folder [Climate Projections](#) a script named `bias_correction_PTHRES.R` is reported, which is the main script used by NOA to bias adjust the daily Regional Climate Model data for the temperature variables (daily maximum, daily minimum and daily mean) as well as daily accumulated precipitation for the Douro Valley region.

The script reads both the daily data for the reference observed gridded dataset as well as the Regional Climate Model data for the periods examined in MED-GOLD and performs bias adjustment using the empirical quantile mapping method ([RD.1], [RD.3]). Before running the script the only action needed is to make sure that the regional climate model data are on the same grid with the reference observed gridded dataset.

The script is written in the R project programming language thus the user is expected to be familiar with the specific programming language. Bias adjustment is performed using the `downscaleR` package ([RD.1 RD.3]).

6.5 Climate Indices

The folder [Climate Indices](#) contains a script written in the Python language named “MEDGOLD_WP3_indices.py”. This script calculates the key climatic indices supplied by Sogrape, which were described in [RD.1], section 4.1. The script requires the climate data to read into an Iris cube beforehand. It will work on both observed and modelled data. This script was used to calculate the bioclimatic indices that users can interrogate using the wine service tool on the Dashboard.

